

Decision support tool for sustainable design of emerging technologies

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The challenges related to rolling out sustainable policies that respect the environment have led to a legislative and normative framework that accompanies the design stage for a product, particularly for companies. However, the associated tools proposed are essentially based on life cycle assessments and remain ill-adapted to studies conducted in the development phases of an emerging technology. Therefore, researchers and engineers are left alone with their environmental responsibility to make choices on the scientific and technological direction and without tools to help inform their considerations. This article provides a decision support tool for sustainable design of emerging technologies. This tool makes it possible to question and consider the environmental challenges related to emerging technologies. Two cases have been studied to illustrate the process and the results obtained: Smart composite materials and fuel cell systems.

Key words: Eco-innovation, design for sustainability, story mapping, product life cycle, smart composite structures, fuel cell.

Introduction

For several years, awareness of environmental challenges has given rise to the emergence of many studies on how to address these issues when developing new products. This is due to the fact that 80% of the environmental impact caused by a product, service, or system is conditioned by the technical choices made during the design stage (Wenzel, Hauschild and Alting 2000). In this context, the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) has also emerged. CSR can be defined as an organisation's responsibility regarding the impact of its decisions and activities on society and the environment. This translates into more ethical and transparent behaviour that contributes to sustainable development (NF ISO 26000 2010). It also seems relevant, even essential, to consider these issues of social responsibility at the level of scientific and technological activities as well as decisions taken during the early stages of the innovation and product

design processes. We will focus more specifically on the concept of the technological module (or emerging technology) and how to give researchers and engineers decision components to make design choices relevant to their environmental responsibility. A technological module can be defined as an invention that is based on a technological component that does not necessarily constitute a finished product. It is in the process of being developed in a laboratory or a company's R&D department and is at a low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) (NF ISO 16290 2013) between 1 (Basic principles observed) and 5 (Technology validated in relevant environment).

At the moment, researchers and engineers mainly use methods and tools for eco-design to help them make choices related to design and development (NF ISO 14-040 2006). Eco-design can be defined as the *“systematic integration of environmental aspects starting from the design and development stages for products (goods and services, systems) with a goal of reducing negative environmental impacts throughout their life cycle at an equivalent or higher level of service. Prior to the design process, this approach aims to find the best balance between the environmental, social, technical, and economic requirements for designing and developing products”* (NF X30-264 2013 8). Many methods and tools, based mostly on Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the product, from extracting the material to its end of lifespan—via its manufacturing, transport, and use—have been developed to help designers take the environment into consideration: ISO 14040 standard in 2006 (ISO 14040:2006), PROMISE method (Verkooyen 1994), Environmental Design of Industrial Products Tool or EDIP Tool (Wenzel, Hauschild and Alting 2000), and EcoReDesign tool (RMIT Centre of Design 1997). For each stage of the life cycle, these various tools operate primarily on the suggestion of a model of environmental inputs/outputs in order to limit severity and toxicity for the environment (Guilloux 2009; Domingo 2013). These tools are based on rich and very thorough

databases. However, they are also extremely expensive in terms of time, human, and economic resources (Guilloux 2009). In addition, they assume that the design of the product under study is being completed. These tools are therefore poorly suited to work concerning technological modules (Guilloux 2009; Domingo 2013) for which many of the points in the life cycle are still unknown (use, standardisation, transport, etc.).

In the context of work focusing on the stages before the design process, it is also common to refer to eco-innovation, which can be defined as: *“developing and putting on the market a product or service that is more respectful of the environment and providing additional value compared to earlier goods/services”* (Teulon 2015). The methods and tools for eco-innovation are based either on lists of environmental criteria or objectives to be achieved, such as those put forward by Issa, Pigosso, McAlloone & Rozenfeld in 2015; on methods for resolving problems, such as TRIZ (Savransky 2000); or tools that are more specifically dedicated to eco-design, e.g. Eco-Systematic (Tyl 2011) and Open Green (Teulon 2015). All of these tools help to guide the thinking during the creativity phase. These criteria seem to be relevant, but not sufficient, in a process of analysing a technological module. Indeed, they have to be adapted or other tools have to be added to consider the specificity of an emerging technology.

There is also the option to use the concept of “design for sustainability (D4S)”, which goes beyond the problems of eco-design and eco-innovation to also focus on social and economic concerns by referring to the three pillars of sustainable development: Person, profit, and planet (UNEP 2009). The main methodological approach stems from benchmarking methods, tools, and design guidelines similar to eco-innovation tools, which should help designers anticipate environmental, social, and economic impacts (UNEP 2009). This approach also proposes anticipating the product life cycle and, in particular, the usage stages through creating a scenario. Many actors in design thinking

and user-centered design are concerned with this scenario of activities for directing design, thanks to prospective tools (Carroll 2000; Nelson, Buisine and Aoussat 2013; Lobbé, et al. 2017). Various tools can be suggested. For example, in 2000, Carroll defined the scenarios as stories in the form of text or a series of illustrations or a storyboard that involves the actors and actions to be taken. These tools, which are based on the principles of storytelling, make it possible to visualise the current or future activities while using a product. Other approaches work using story mapping and tools like the “user journey map” or “consumer journey map”. These use graphs to make it possible to visualise and assess positive and negative experiences for the user testing the products (Martin and Hanington 2012; Tharon 2014). Once again, these different tools help guide the thinking process during the creativity phase and are still not adapted to analyse the impacts of a technology module.

The literature review highlighted the lack of tools to question the environmental challenges related to a technological module in order to give decision components to make sustainable design choices. We also highlighted the wealth of heuristic approaches and the need, in a sustainable design process, to project possible and probable futures in order to anticipate its environmental impacts during its full life cycle as soon as possible. These story mapping tools are particularly interesting with regard to studying potential futures for a technological module and also for better anticipating the possible and probable environmental impacts. These various elements make it possible to offer a decision support tool for the sustainable design of technological modules. This tool is presented in the following section. Then, two study cases are proposed. Finally, a discussion on the proposed tool is conducted.

Decision support tool for sustainable design

In order to study the environmental impacts of a technological module and help researchers and engineers make more informed decisions in sustainable design, a tool based on a five-step approach is proposed.

(1) Establishing the project team

The project team conducting the analysis must have skills in the technological module, but also be capable of looking at the module from a neutral, dispassionate, and cross-disciplinary perspective. It must therefore have, at minimum, two experts. The first is an expert in the technological module and the second an expert in potential and anticipated uses, e.g. an expert in design thinking. Depending on the complexity of the technological module and the number of disciplines involved, it may be suitable to include several technical experts.

(2) Analysing the technological module

For the expert in design thinking, the aim of this stage is to be fully immersed in the field by analysing the field's scientific literature and trends (Martin and Hanington 2012) to collect knowledge on the technological module. Its usage environments and potential uses—and possibly users, if this group has been identified at this stage—can be also analysed. Therefore, a study is conducted on the module's basic characteristics, materials used, manufacturing processes, technical systems used, standards and regulations in force, and economic features (Quarante 1994; Ulrich and Eppinger 1999; Carroll 2000; Hassenzahl 2003; Arhipainen and Tähti 2003; NF ISO 14-040 2006; Mahlke 2007; Desmet and Hekkert 2007; Brown 2009; Ashby 2010; Atasoy and Martens 2011). Sessions can also be conducted to observe the different stages of the life cycle, e.g.

manufacturing stage, if they are already known. Using the information collected, common representations (Darses De Montmollin 2004) shown as analysis boards (Martin and Hanington 2012) may also be put together by the project team. A common representation can be defined as a common knowledge profile that encourages sharing knowledge and communication between the different actors involved in a project. All of the common representations created should enable a clear view of the technological module's characteristics, from the perspective of uses, users, competitive technology, performance, and integration into its usage environment.

(3) Constructing a life cycle map for a technological module

Heavily inspired by mapping tools, this stage aims to build the product's map throughout all of the stages in its life cycle. This new tool is called a life cycle map. To direct the implementation of this scripting stage, as well as the following stages, we suggest the template presented in Figure 1. The stages of the life cycles, sometimes adapted according to the type of product, are shown in the upper part of the figure. In this stage, the experts must complete the section at the centre: Actions. Without aiming to be exhaustive, this concerns identifying the actions linked to different interactions between actors in the life cycle and the module, in view of the characteristics identified beforehand.

Figure 1. Template of a life cycle map

(4) Identifying environmental and social impacts

To complete this product life cycle map, the project team must conduct an analysis of the environmental and social risks and opportunities for each action identified. From these risks and opportunities, the resulting environmental and social impacts will be derived for each action. To facilitate reflection, risk analysis and heuristic eco-innovation tools (UNEP 2009; Issa, et al. 2015) may be used.

(5) Identifying scientific and technological problems

The result obtained therefore makes it possible to use a sole representation to visualise all the environmental and social impacts related to a technological module with regard to current knowledge of the field, prospective observation, and analysis of potential usages. Technological experts who want to question the research approaches available can also consciously make decisions by concentrating in particular on the inherent risks of the technology in terms of the social and environmental impacts. These elements are clearly visible on the lower part of the life cycle map. For each risk and its associated impacts, it is possible to think about scientific challenges that would help in overcoming them. This opens the way to the construction of a roadmap for the development of the technological module. In an extreme case, it is also possible to question the relevance of pursuing certain technological developments, if they are deemed to have too much impact on the environment or society.

Case studies: Smart composite structures and fuel cell systems

In order to highlight the relevance of our approach, two case studies have been conducted: the first on smart composite structures and the second on fuel cells.

Smart composite structures

By composite structures, we are referring to structures made from a combination of at least two materials with different properties (Campbell 2010). This combination makes it possible to obtain better properties than would be possible with the materials taken individually. Composite materials currently contain high-resistance fibres that are lost in a matrix (Gay 2014). Smart composite structures are structures that can change their properties depending on the stimuli. Given a certain input, they produce a predictable and repeatable response that is called an output (Esther, et al. 2014). In this study, we will focus on smart composite structures produced at the Université de Technologie de Belfort-Montbéliard, France. We will look at polymer matrix composite materials into which we integrated piezoelectric transducers during the manufacturing stage (Meyer and Lachat 2015; Lachat and Meyer 2017).

We detail the five stages of our approach for the smart composite structures.

(1) Establishing the project team

During this study, the analyses were conducted by a duo of experts: an expert in design thinking and an expert in intelligent composite structures but outside the project of the technological module studied to validate the analysis.

(2) Analysis: Smart composite structures.

14 common representations, presented in Figure 2, were established by the design thinking expert for the smart composite structures study. Five boards were created to present the materials used and four concentrated on the operational characteristics of the smart composite structures. Two boards presenting the fields of application were also presented. With regard to the environment, two boards were put forward. The first focused on all types of physical environment—gas, solid, liquid, animal, vegetation, land,

Figure 3. Map representing the life cycle of smart composite structures

(4) Identifying environmental and social impacts

Based on the actions defined in the previous stage, the risks and opportunities in relation to the environmental and social issues were identified. Using this analysis, the design thinking expert and the technological module expert studied the environmental and social impacts by using, in particular, the guidelines for sustainable design and eco-responsibility (UNEP 2009; Issa, et al. 2015). The life cycle map was completed as proposed in Figure 4. This representation summarizes the possible positive and negative environmental and social impacts in connection with the various stages of the life cycle of the technological module.

Figure 4. Map representing the life cycle of smart composite structures with analyses of risks, opportunities, and environmental and social impacts.

(5) Identifying scientific and technological problems

On the basis of this life cycle map, the expert in the technological module was able to extract a number of paths to consider. An analysis of the representations clearly shows that using smart composite structures makes sense in terms of environmental impact only if these structures reduce the impacts related to the initial composite structures.

The increase in production volume for composite structures (10 million tonnes per year globally) leads to a considerable increase in the waste from manufacturing processes and duration of the life cycle. The instrumentation of these composite structures leads to new environmental impacts, but gives new functions to these structures. In a study on minimising environmental impacts, the functionalisation of structures may be a solution that provides a response to the weaknesses of composite structures. It is possible to optimise the lifespan, monitor transport, inspect structural health, and reduce risks in terms of premature wear and tear, industrial accidents, etc. It appears essential to be able to quantify and qualify the benefit of functionalising smart composite structures with regard to risks of damage and shocks. Likewise, it is for experts in the field to define manufacturing processes based on their functionalisation in order to minimise the risk of ending up with poorly designed and non-operational structures during manufacturing. Therefore, work must be carried out to be able to measure and correct the manufacturing process in real time and to develop a manufacturing method that allows precise and repeatable instrument positioning. The analysis also clearly highlights the need to conduct research activities in terms of using bio-sourced materials, in addition to the need to develop both techniques for extracting the elements integrated at the heart of the material, including rare metals, and techniques for optimising the structure to facilitate this extraction.

Fuel cell systems

A fuel cell is a technical device that makes it possible to convert the chemical energy contained in hydrogen into electrical energy and heat, without producing air pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, or noise pollution (Li 2005). These claims are only true if hydrogen is produced cleanly from renewable resources. There is a wide variety of cells available depending on their strength and the application context. The one most frequently studied due to its use for transport (Alaswad, et al. 2016) is the Proton-Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC). In the context of this work, we will be concentrating on this type of cell. We will consider not only the cell on its own, but also its direct environment that allows it to operate: Electronic controls and auxiliary systems.

(1) Establishing the project team

For this module, the analyses were conducted by a design thinking expert and two fuel cell experts from outside the project.

(2) Analysis: Fuel cells.

Nine common representations, presented in Figure 5, were established by the design thinking expert for the fuel cells study. Three boards were used to present the characteristics and performance of fuel cells and hydrogen. One board presenting the fields of application was also presented. With regard to the environment, three boards were put forward to more broadly investigate the potential environments for use: At home, at work, in hospitals, etc. Lastly, two boards specific to the module were created to study potential users and their activities.

Figure 5. Analysis boards for fuel cells (A – Fuel cell definitions and applications; B – Environments of use; C –Potential end-users)

(3) Constructing life cycle maps for a technological module

Thanks to the common representations established previously, two life cycle maps representing the life cycles of the cell and hydrogen and the cell's main energy source were defined. During the analysis of the fuel cell, it actually appeared that the scientific and technological issues of the cell were inseparable from those for hydrogen. As a result, two distinct maps, illustrated in Figures 6 and 7, were developed.

Figure 6. Map representing the life cycle of a fuel cell

Figure 7. Map representing the life cycle of hydrogen

(4) Identifying environmental and social impacts

The risks and opportunities in relation to the environmental and social issues were identified. Then, by using, in particular the guidelines for sustainable design and eco-responsibility (UNEP 2009; Issa, et al. 2015), the design thinking expert and the technological module experts studied the environmental and social aspects for each issue. Figures 8 and 9 present these two analyses.

Figure 8. Map representing the life cycle of a fuel cell with analyses of risks, opportunities, and environmental and social impacts.

Figure 9. Map representing the life cycle of hydrogen with analyses of risks, opportunities, and environmental and social impacts.

(5) Identifying scientific and technological problems

Based on these two maps, fuel cell experts were able to extract a number of research axes to consider.

Concerning fuel cells, the proposed map highlighted issues related to the constitutive materials of the cell core. The use of platinum and fossil fuel materials should be minimised. Improving the electrolyte membrane could eliminate the use of fluoride. It is also essential to optimise the architecture of the cell, its auxiliaries, ageing process and maintenance, recyclability, reliability, etc.

For hydrogen, the life cycle map revealed the need for research in three areas: The production of hydrogen from renewable resources that are low-cost in terms of economy and energy; the hydrogen production chain, considering the economic and social challenges; and lastly, the materials and product architecture to safely hold, store, and transport hydrogen. All of these scientific barriers are clearly identified in the literature and supported by various scientific communities.

Discussion

Our objective was to propose a decision support tool that is adapted to researchers and engineers, allowing them to question and consider the social and environmental challenges related to the technological modules they studied.

Our methodological approach is based, on one hand, on close cross-disciplinary collaboration between a design thinking expert and experts in the field being studied and, on the other hand, the use of a tool for scripting the life cycle (Martin and Hanington 2012; Tharon 2014) to anticipate the environmental and social risks, opportunities, and impacts related to using the technological module. This tool is based on the user journey map and is called the life cycle map. Following many authors who are working on the

idea of collaborative design to support consideration of usages (Aoussat, Christofol and Coq 2000; Lobbé, et al. 2017), these initial results strengthen our conviction that there is a need for a cross-disciplinary team to work through the methodology. During the technological module's discovery stage, it is vital to include both technical and non-technical data linked to usage, social trends, etc.

The relevance of our tool is demonstrated for two case studies: smart composite structures and fuel cells. The maps obtained question the main scientific and technological obstacles related to these technological modules. For each case study, these technological modules were submitted for evaluation to researchers who are specialists in the field and external to the study being conducted. The researchers consulted validated the quality and comprehensiveness of the mapping in the field studied. These two case studies are substantial and complementary. Smart composite structures are actually at a low TRL and are still at the stage of prototypes in a laboratory. In contrast, the fuel cell is at a higher TRL. It is industrialised and commercialised, even though it has still not entirely found its market. The results obtained clearly map the scientific and technological challenges of the field with regard to environmental and social concerns and therefore the associated design paths. The goal is to optimise the technological module's design during development, thanks to the analysis conducted. The resulting reports can absolutely be used as specifications for the next stages in design. To direct the design stages after this report, we recommend adopting responsible and sustainable approaches to design taken from trends such as user-based design, design thinking, and design for sustainability. The following stage in our approach is to include the potential end-users in the process of thinking about technological modules, so that they can actively participate in the design process by expressing their needs, wants, and perception of the technological module throughout the design process. From this perspective, studies with potential users are

underway on smart composite structures in order to identify innovative and sustainable uses for this technological module (Bazzaro and Meyer 2022).

Although our methodological proposal targets a systematic approach to the product life cycle, it does not anticipate interactions, especially in terms of environmental and social impacts, between the various stages of the life cycle. In contrast to our proposal, the traditional tools for LCA take these interactions into account and offer extremely astute quantitative analyses. However, in accordance with the works of Guilloux in 2009 and Domingo in 2013, these are poorly suited to our concerns, in our opinion. For example, the first step of an LCA consists of defining a functional unit. How can the functional unit of a structure be precisely defined at the prototype stage when neither the use nor the conditions for use have been defined? It is of course possible to work based on a hypothesis or scenario, but is it suitable to have as many hypotheses as weak data in an LCA? Can development really be based on the results obtained? Therefore, although our proposal does not allow a complete quantitative analysis, it still establishes foundations for considering new scientific works to optimise the technological module studied. Regularly updating the product life cycle map should ensure that each new advancement in a direction is not to the detriment of other components in the product and does not generate new environmental and social impacts.

As for many methods and tools that question environmental and social impacts, many unsuitable results can be extracted from our methodological proposal. Only a complete and scientifically honest analysis can lead to reliable results. Furthermore, it is then the individual responsibility of each expert in the field studied to draw the research to be conducted from these results, while making informed decisions on their scientific direction. In extreme cases, it is imaginable that the development of a technological module may be abandoned due to the social or environmental impact that is deemed too

substantial and that no development path could improve.

References

Alaswad, A, A Baroutaji, H Achour, J Carton, A Al Makky, and A-G Olabi.

"Developments in fuel cell technologies in the transport sector." *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2016: 16499-16508.

Aoussat, A, H Christofol, and M.L Coq. "The new product design - a transverse approach." *Journal of Engineering Design* 11, no. 4 (2000): 399-417.

Arhippainen, L, and M Tähti. "Empirical Evaluation of User Experience in Two Adaptive Mobile Application Prototypes." *Communication presented at the 2nd International Conference on Mobile and Ubiquitous Multimedia*, 2003: 27-34.

Ashby, M F. *Materials Selection in Mechanical Design*. 4e. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2010.

Atasoy, B, and J.-B Martens. "Crafting User Experiences by Incorporating Dramaturgical Techniques of Storytelling." *Proceedings of the Second Conference on Creativity and Innovation in Design, DESIRE '11*. New York: ACM, 2011. 91-102.

Bazzaro, Florence, et Yann Meyer. "User-centred design approach with misidentified end-users: case study for smart composite structures." *Journal of Engineering Design*, 2022: 1-14.

Brown, T. *Change by Design: How Design Thinking Transforms Organizations and Inspires Innovation*. Harper Business, 2009.

Campbell, F C. *Structural composite materials*. ASM international., 2010.

Carroll, J M. "Five reasons for scenario-based design." *Interacting with Computer* 13, no. 1 (2000): 43-60.

- Darses De Montmollin, F. "La conception participative: vers une théorie de la conception centrée sur l'établissement d'une intelligibilité mutuelle." In *Le consommateur au coeur de l'innovation [en ligne]*, by J Caelen, 25-41. Paris: CNRS Edition, 2004.
- Desmet, P, and P Hekkert. "Framework of product experience." *International journal of design* 1, no. 1 (2007): 57-66.
- Domingo, L. *Méthodologie d'éco-conception orientée utilisation*. Thèse de Doctorat de l'Université de Grenoble, 2013.
- Esther, L, A Piselli, J Faucheu, D Delafosse, and B Del Curto. "Smart materials: development of new sensory experiences through stimuli responsive materials." *5th STS Italia Conference A Matter of Design: Making Society through Science and Technology*. STS Italia., 2014. 367-382.
- Gay, D. *Composite materials: design and applications*. CRC press., 2014.
- Guilloux, G. *Ecodesign, du contexte au produit : contribution méthodologique à l'intégration de l'environnement dans les métiers du design industriel*. Thèse de Doctorat Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines de Saint-Etienne & de L'université Polytechnique de Valencia, 2009.
- Hassenzahl, M. "The Thing and I: Understanding the Relationship Between User and Product." In *Funology, Human-Computer Interaction Series*, edited by M.A Blythe, K Overbeeke, A.F Monk and P.C Wright, 31-42. Springer Netherlands,, 2003.
- Issa, I I, D C A Pigosso, T C McAloone, and H Rozenfeld. "Leading product-related environmental performance indicators: a selection guide and database." *Journal of Cleaner Production* 108 (2015): 321-330.
- Lachat, R, and Y Meyer. Patent No. WO2017013346. 2017.

- Li, X. *Principles of fuel cells*. New-York: Taylor & Francis Group, 2005.
- Lobbé, J, F Bazzaro, M Charrier, and J-C Sagot. "Taking into account life situation during a co-creativity session: an exploratory study." *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference of Engineering Design (ICED17)*. Vancouver, 2017.
- Mahlke, S. "User experience: usability, aesthetics and emotions in human-technology interaction." *Towards a UX Manifesto*, 2007: 26-30.
- Martin, B, and B Hanington. *Universal Methods of Design: 100 Ways to Research Complex Problems, Develop Innovative Ideas, and Design Effective Solutions*. Edited by Eyrolles. Rockport Publishers, 2012.
- Meyer, Y, and R Lachat. "Smart composite structures: Benefits, technical issues and potential applications." *JEC Composites Magazine*, no. 105 (2015).
- Nelson, J, S Buisine, and A Aoussat. "Anticipating the use of future things: Towards a framework for prospective use analysis in innovation design projects." *Applied Ergonomics* 44, no. 6 (2013): 948-956.
- NF ISO 14-040. *Environmental management -- Life cycle assessment --*. AFNOR, 2006.
- NF ISO 16290. *Space system - Definition of the technology readiness levels (TRLs) and their criteria of assessment*. AFNOR, 2013.
- NF ISO 26000. *Guidance on social responsibility*. AFNOR, 2010.
- NF X30-264. *Environmental management - Assistance for the implementation of an ecodesign methodology - Management environnemental*. AFNOR, 2013.
- Quarante, D. *Elements du design industriel*. 2. Paris: Polytechnica, 1994.
- RMIT Centre of Design. *Introduction to EcoReDesign : improving the environmental performance of manufactured products*. Melbourne, 1997.
- Savransky, S D. *Engineering of Creativity: Introduction to TRIZ Methodology of Inventive Problem Solving*. CRC Press., 2000.

- Teulon, H. *Le guide de l'éco-innovation: Eco-concevoir pour gagner en compétitivité*. Eyrolles, 2015.
- Tharon, H. "Journey Mapping: A brief overview." *Communication Design Quarterly* 2, no. 3 (2014): 10-13.
- Tyl, B. *L'apport de la créativité dans les processus d'éco-innovation - Proposition de l'outil EcoASIT pour favoriser l'éco-idéation de systèmes durables. Thèse de Doctorat en Mécanique*. Université Sciences et Technologies - Bordeaux I., 2011.
- Ulrich, K T, and S D. Eppinger. *Product Design and Development: second edition 1999 - Fifth edition 2012*. McGraw-Hill Companies, 1999.
- UNEP. *Design for Sustainability - A step-by-step approach*. TU Delft, 2009.
- Verkooyen, H. *PROMISE Handleiding voor Milieugerichte Produkt Ontwikkeling (PROMISE: Manual for ecodesign)*. The Netherlands: SdU Uitgeverij, Den Haag, 1994.
- Wenzel, H, M Z. Hauschild, and L Alting. *Environmental Assessment of Products: Volume 1: Methodology, Tools and Case Studies in Product Development*. Springer. 2000.

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